

SECTION OF SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE IT OUTSOURCING INDUSTRY IN UKRAINE

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Abstract

The article provides a comprehensive analysis of the current state and development trends in the IT outsourcing market in Ukraine. It is noted that in the last decade there has been a rapid growth in the provision of outsourced IT services by Ukrainian companies. In 2021, the IT outsourcing market reached \$5 billion, which is a 20% annual growth rate. This indicates Ukraine's significant potential in this area.

It is stated that our country is a leader in the IT outsourcing market in Eastern Europe, outpacing Poland, Romania, Hungary and other countries. At the same time, globally Ukraine lags behind India and China. The main exports are software development and IT consulting services for US and EU companies. The key advantages are the high qualifications and relatively low cost of specialists.

The factors constraining the growth of IT outsourcing in Ukraine are noted: imperfect legislation, shortage of personnel, low language proficiency, high business risks, etc. To realize the potential, it is proposed to improve the regulatory framework of the industry, upgrade specialist training, and create favorable conditions for IT business.

It is concluded that given the implementation of these measures, IT outsourcing can become the engine of economic growth and a catalyst for positive structural changes in Ukraine. The export of IT services is projected to grow to \$5-7 billion annually. Outsourcing will facilitate Ukraine's integration into the global economy as a high-tech partner.

Keywords: IT outsourcing, information technology, outsourcing in Ukraine, IT services, IT services export, IT professionals, freelancing.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Information technology is gaining increasing importance in the modern world and plays a vital role in the economic development of any country. Ukraine is experiencing rapid growth in the IT industry, in particular in the field of IT outsourcing. IT outsourcing involves transferring individual IT processes or projects of the customer company for servicing to external IT companies on a contractual basis.

The global demand for IT outsourcing services is growing as it allows companies to optimize costs, focus on core business and gain access to highly qualified specialists. Ukraine has significant potential for the development of IT outsourcing due to the availability of skilled IT professionals, favorable economic conditions and geographical proximity to European countries. In recent years, revenues from the export of computer and information services in Ukraine have been growing rapidly, already exceeding \$5 billion annually.

However, the IT outsourcing industry in Ukraine faces certain challenges that hinder its further development. These include a shortage of skilled personnel, imperfect legislation in the IT field, insufficient intellectual property protection, difficulties entering new markets, etc. The article aims to comprehensively analyze the current state, key trends and problems in the development of the IT outsourcing industry in Ukraine.

The study will allow a comprehensive assessment of the potential of IT outsourcing for the Ukrainian economy and its competitive advantages in the global market. Particular attention will be paid to analyzing the growth dynamics of the industry, the structure of IT services provided through outsourcing, and the geography of exports of such services. In addition, based on

the identified problems, recommendations will be made to stimulate further growth of the IT outsourcing sector and increase its competitiveness on the world stage.

Given the growing importance of the IT industry for the Ukrainian economy, the study of the chosen topic is extremely relevant. The results of the analysis of IT outsourcing development will be of great practical importance and will help determine further steps for building this promising industry in Ukraine.

ANALYSIS OF RECENT STUDIES AND PUBLICATIONS

IT outsourcing is one of the most dynamic and promising industries in Ukraine, attracting the attention of many researchers.

In particular, the trends and prospects for the development of the IT outsourcing market in Ukraine have been studied by I. Ostrovskiy, M. Pityulych, S. Kulytskyi and others [13,14]. They focus on the positive factors for the growth of this industry, including the availability of skilled and relatively inexpensive IT personnel, favorable taxation conditions, and geographical proximity to EU countries.

Problems and risks hindering the development of IT outsourcing in Ukraine have been explored by N. Kraus [8], T. Knyazyeva [7], A. Starostina [16]. These include political and economic instability, imperfect legislation in the field of intellectual property protection, shortage of personnel due to the outflow of IT specialists abroad.

Foreign scientists R. Hirschheim, B. Nicholson [4], S. Balaji [1] also analyze the risks of IT outsourcing and ways to minimize them, as well as issues of data protection and intellectual property.

Among foreign researchers, IT outsourcing has been addressed by T.Lacity, L.P. Willcocks, M.C. Lacity, D.F. Feeny [2], J.D. Rottman, O.E. Williamson and others.

In particular, they have analyzed the motivation for companies to outsource IT services, success factors and reasons for failure of such projects, strategies for managing relationships with IT providers [9].

J. Yip, J. Roos focused on protecting intellectual property and confidential data in IT outsourcing, as well as the impact of cultural differences on the interaction between foreign companies and outsourcers [17].

S. Manning examined the benefits of IT outsourcing for small and medium-sized enterprises [10]. Y. Goo and R. Huang analyzed the impact of outsourcing on innovation and competitiveness [3].

However, a comprehensive analysis of the dynamics, structure, geography of IT outsourcing in Ukraine and its contribution to the country's economy is currently lacking. The proposed article aims to fill this gap, summarize existing research, and assess industry prospects based on statistical data. This will identify key trends, challenges and opportunities for further growth of IT outsourcing in Ukraine.

OBJECTIVES OF THE ARTICLE

The purpose of this article is to analyze the trends and patterns in the development of the IT outsourcing industry in Ukraine, to study our country's position in the global IT outsourcing market. This will allow us to determine the scope of outsourced IT services provided in Ukraine, examine the structure and geography of exports of such services, and assess Ukraine's competitive advantages against global trends in the field of IT outsourcing.

THE MAIN MATERIAL OF THE RESEARCH

No country can achieve sustainable economic growth without effective participation in the international division of labor. This is due to the uneven access of states to global resources and capital, which determines the globalization of the economy. By establishing foreign economic relations, countries can focus on the key areas of their activities.

In recent decades, the information and communication technology industry has demonstrated some of the highest growth rates in the world economy. This sector significantly affects the development of the global economy. The introduction of the latest technologies allows optimizing business processes, using resources more efficiently, and accelerating data exchange. Information technology can be used to manage and control almost all business processes.

As a result, companies face the problem of high costs for IT support of their activities. This issue is acute in developed countries where competition is much higher. Therefore, companies are forced to optimize costs and improve the efficiency of all departments, including IT.

One of the tools for solving this problem may be the outsourcing of information technology - the transfer of IT functions to external companies. Regarding the concept of information technology (IT) outsourcing, this is the practice of transferring all or part of a company's IT functions from the customer company to the contractor. The most common types of IT outsourcing today include:

Transferring secondary infrastructure support services abroad (ITO - infrastructure IT outsourcing);

Transferring non-critical business processes that require significant amounts of unskilled labor abroad (BPO - business process outsourcing);

Custom software development [6].

Outsourcing is a controversial process that has both advantages and disadvantages for companies using it and for the country as a whole. The main advantages for companies include:

- the ability to focus on core activities;
- reducing its costs;
- risk minimization by transferring it to other companies;
- obtaining financial flexibility.

The disadvantages of IT outsourcing:

- loss of full control over the IT infrastructure;
- dependence on the contractor, in particular regarding security;
- reduced productivity of own staff [5].

The implementation and management of IT outsourcing can compensate for its shortcomings.

In Ukraine, there is a positive trend in the development of the information technology sector as opposed to other industries. Currently, the global IT outsourcing market is estimated at 300 billion US dollars, and with a volume of 5 billion, Ukraine has prospects for growth in its activity and presence in this market.

India and China are leaders in the IT outsourcing market, but Eastern Europe is also an attractive location. Ukraine is one of the largest developers of information products and IT outsourcing in the region. The development of IT outsourcing in Ukraine is already yielding positive macroeconomic effects and can contribute to structural changes in the economy. Among the effects of IT outsourcing are:

- improvement in the structure of the labor market;
- inflow of foreign currency and improvement of the balance of payments;
- increase in domestic demand;
- overcoming the stratification of the population;
- strengthening the financial security of the state.

Over the past decade, there has been growth in the IT outsourcing market in Ukraine - from 1.8 billion dollars in 2012 to almost 5 billion dollars in 2021. Only the full-scale invasion by the Russian Federation into Ukraine led to a decline in this trend (Figure 1).

Figure 1. – Dynamics of the development of the outsourcing market in Ukraine for the period from 2012 to 2022

On average, the annual growth rate of the IT outsourcing market in Ukraine during the pre-war period was 20%, which is a very high indicator. During this period, the market volume is comparable to Ukrainian exports of steel and metal products; during the war, this indicator decreased, but the rates of its decline are insignificant compared to the product sectors of the economy.

Assessing the state of IT outsourcing, it is necessary to compare the market volume of Ukraine with competing countries in Europe. Poland, Romania, Hungary, and the Czech Republic are the European leaders in market volume. Ukraine occupies the first place in the region with an indicator of 5 billion dollars. At the same time, it is difficult to compare Ukraine with giants like India, where the market volume reaches 86 billion dollars.

According to the IT Ukraine Association, our country ranks 4th in the world in the number of certified IT professionals. Also, Ukraine is among the TOP-30 locations for software development. This indicates the enormous growth potential of the industry [12].

The potential for the development of IT outsourcing in Ukraine lies in the fact that increasing volumes do not require large investments in fixed assets, since the main resource is human capital. Ukrainian professionals are involved in the development of information products on behalf of companies from Europe and the USA. Freelancing services are also common.

According to a study by Topdev, in 2021 Ukraine retained its leadership in Eastern Europe in the development of information products on a freelance basis, despite an 8% reduction in its share.

Ukraine continues to lead in Eastern Europe in the volume of IT freelancing, executing a third of the relevant orders in the region. On one hand, the spread of freelancing can negatively affect the country due to losses in budget revenues. On the other hand, it contributes to the influx of currency, an increase in the purchasing power of the population, and the formation of a middle class.

A high share of freelancing indicates the imperfection of IT industry regulation in Ukraine. Currently, our state has not fully realized the potential of the IT outsourcing market, as evidenced by the steady demand for qualified IT professionals. A balanced policy for the development of outsourcing can transform it into a powerful factor of economic growth. Among the main obstacles to its development are the following:

- the absence of legislative regulation of outsourcing;
- insufficient promotion of the domestic market;
- the low level of english proficiency among professionals;
- high business risks;
- the instability of the economic and political situation.

Therefore, IT outsourcing can become a leading direction of Ukraine's exports, provided that existing problems are overcome. This sector must gain strategic importance. This means granting privileges to IT companies and access to credit resources. Also, changes in personnel training are required.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the conducted research, it can be asserted that information technology outsourcing is one of the most successful and promising sectors of Ukraine's economy. Over the last decade, the IT outsourcing industry has demonstrated impressive growth rates, increasing to up to 5 billion US dollars. The average annual growth rates have reached up to 20%. Such high indicators suggest that Ukraine has significant potential in this area.

Currently, our state is the undisputed leader in the IT outsourcing market of Eastern Europe, surpassing in service volume countries such as Poland, Romania, Hungary, and other nations of the region. However, on a global scale, Ukraine falls behind giants like India or China. The export base consists of services in software development and IT consulting, predominantly provided to companies in the USA and EU countries. The

high qualification of Ukrainian IT professionals at a relatively low price is the main competitive advantage of our country in the global outsourcing market.

At the same time, there are several factors that hinder further growth of IT outsourcing in Ukraine. Among them are the imperfection of legislative regulation of the industry, a shortage of highly qualified personnel, an insufficient level of foreign language proficiency, high business risks, and more. To realize the existing potential, it is necessary to improve the legal framework of the IT industry's operation, promote the improvement of professional training, ensure favorable tax and credit conditions for IT companies, and create mechanisms for state support in entering new markets. Provided these measures are implemented, IT outsourcing can become the locomotive of Ukraine's economic growth and a catalyst for positive structural changes in the economy. IT services export has the potential to reach 5-7 billion US dollars per year, contributing to the integration of Ukraine into the global economy as a high-tech partner.

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